

**Notes—Forthcoming Energy and Climate Law
Quarterly—2021**

DISMISSAL OF A JUDICIAL REVIEW IN ENVIRONMENTAL
MATTERS

*[Ms Elaine Martin v. Folkestone and Hythe District
Council
The Queen (on the application of Ms Elaine Martin) v.
Folkestone and Hythe District Council
Case No: CO/3409/2019
High Court of Justice Queen's Bench Division
Planning Court
22 June 2020]*

An application for planning permission was submitted. The former was then validated and has indeed resulted in the present case.

In support of the first ground, the applicant states that the members of the Board were misled as to whether or not there had been a breach of certain elements of the TM8 and LR9 policies. In support of this argument, he argues that the panel's report did not allow for a determination of the degree of compliance or non-compliance of certain elements of these policies with the development plan.

The applicant argues that the elements of the commission's report provided only a description of the proposal and that the passages devoted to the design of the building did not provide relevant information, in particular as to whether or not the building was small scale and low-rise. In this sense, he argues that while the commission's report deals with the amount of open space contained in the proposals, it does not provide an adequate or appropriate assessment of the impact on the open character of the site. Similarly, the applicant submits that, as far as the RMC is concerned, the commission's report does not adequately identify the nature of the breach of the policy, although it does refer to the harm caused to its setting.

Where the LR9 policy is to be addressed, the applicant argues that the panel's report did not adequately address the issue of whether or not there

was an unacceptable loss of environmental quality, whereas the panel's report refers to a range of environmental factors, such as the impact on the landscape and nature conservation issues. Thus, a reading of the committee's report does not reveal any aspect that directly addresses the question of whether or not the impact on the quality of the environment was acceptable. Consequently, the applicant submits that the reference in the commission's report to the conclusion that the proposals were contrary to the development plan was not sufficient to address the content of the legal obligation. It would have been fundamental to provide the committee members with specific assessments in relation to those key policy elements of the development plan relating to the site, as the absence of those elements is likely to have misled the members. Thus, the decision is unlawful, especially as it did not contain any evidence of an assessment of the extent of the breach of the policies of the development plan.

The applicant's first ground had been found to be unsubstantiated and therefore had to be rejected. The judge pointed out in this respect that he was not in a position to conclude that the members had been misled by the commission's report or that any legal deficiency in the elements made available to them would have influenced their decision. In that sense, he states that the commission examined in its report, in a reasonable manner and on a thematic basis, the problem of the quality of the environment, which implies the scope of the relevant environmental issues such as the occurrence of damage, the assessment of the nature or extent of the damage. However, the central question of whether the impact on environmental quality was acceptable or not was addressed in the agents' conclusions, which should be read as a whole.

As to the second ground, the applicant argued that the issue of flood risk had not been fundamentally examined, which led the panel members to conclude in their report that there were no objections to development based on flood risk and the sequential test.

In this respect, the applicant objects to the defendant's failure to apply the sequential test and also to have sought to identify sites with a lower flood risk in order to prevent the risks identified on the EE flood maps and wave overtopping. According to its allegations, the defendant erred in not relying on the risk assessment maps contained in the SFRA, as this

led to a failure to differentiate the flood risk identified from the EE flood maps from the risk assessment carried out in the SFRA. In this respect, it should be noted, in the applicant's words, that the policy and its explanatory text referred to the need to study the existence or not of appropriate site alternatives by applying the sequential test, knowing that the site was located in an area identified as being at risk of flooding by the EA flood maps. This implied that only in the absence of a suitable site alternative would it be adequate to refer to the SFRA hazard maps.

This second ground of the applicant had been found to be unsubstantiated and therefore had to be rejected. The reasons for this rejection are twofold.

Firstly, he points out that the terms of the committee's report could have been expressed more precisely and clearly. It should be noted that, in the authorities' view, a "committee report should not be read in an overly forensic manner or with excessive rigour. It should be borne in mind that these documents are presented to the commission as an aid to understanding the issues and to decision-making and should be read in this light". However, there was certainly a pre-existing error, particularly with regard to the fact that there was a minor error in the extent of this area, but it was not considered to be significant in light of the rest of the agents' analysis. This error had been caused by the fact that when the EE floodplain maps were revised, part of the site had now ended up in flood zone 3. However, it appeared that having considered the risks associated with wave overtopping and the proposed mitigation measures and the issue of finished ground levels, based on the SFRA's conclusions, "that the parts of the site proposed for residential development did not present any risk of flooding in 2115 due to climate change, and as such the proposals were consistent with the flood risk policy, including the sequential test."

Concerning the correct interpretation of the relevant flood risk policies, the judge considered that the approach adopted in the commission's report, based on the SFRA and having specified that the proposed development was located in an area not subject to flood risk, reflected the correct understanding of the national policy and planning guidelines. In this sense, it is clear that under paragraph 158, which gives effect to the principle identified in paragraph 155, the sequential test, which is central to new developments in areas with the

lowest flood risk, will be applied on the basis of the SFRA's findings.

In the light of all these considerations, the judge considered that none of the pleas raised by the applicant were well-founded and that the application for judicial review should be dismissed.

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